

REBUILDING GOVERNMENT TRUST AND EFFECTIVE DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA

Kestin Ebimorbowei Pondi, and Michael Ifeanyi Anoka

Department of Public Administration University of Benin, Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract: The study examined the effect of Rebuilding Government Trust on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to; examine the effect of fair and free elections on effective Democratic Governance and evaluate the effect of Accountability mechanisms on effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria. The study adopts a descriptive research survey. A structured questionnaire design with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data for the study. The data was analyzed using Smart PLS version 4.0 with structural equation models. The result revealed that there is a statistically significance positive effect of fair and free elections on democratic governance ($\beta=0.686$; T-Statistic = 8.193; P values < 0.001). Also, the result indicates that the accountability mechanism has no statistically significant effect on the democratic governance ($\beta=-0.009$; T-Statistic = 0.106; P values =0.916) of Nigeria. The study concludes that Rebuilding Government Trust has a significant effect on Democratic Governance in Nigeria. The study recommended among others that the government should reform and enforce electoral laws to prevent fraud, vote-buying, and other irregularities, and ensure the independence and capacity of electoral commissions to conduct elections impartially and effectively.

Keywords: *Democratic, Governance, Government, Rebuilding, Trust*

1.1 Introduction

Trust between citizens and their government is a cornerstone of a functioning and stable society. When this trust is strong, it enables effective governance, fosters civic engagement, and underpins the legitimacy of political institutions. However, in many parts of the world, this essential trust has been significantly eroded due to factors such as corruption, inefficiency, political instability, and unmet public expectations. Rebuilding government trust is a critical and multifaceted challenge (World Bank. 2020). It requires comprehensive efforts to improve transparency, accountability, and responsiveness within governmental institutions. Transparency ensures that governmental actions and decisions are open and accessible to the public, fostering a sense of honesty and integrity. Accountability mechanisms hold public officials responsible for their actions, ensuring that they act in the best interests of the populace. Responsiveness guarantees that the government listens to and addresses the needs and concerns of its citizens (Salako and Ajibade 2019).

The process of restoring trust also involves combating corruption, which is often a major source of public disillusionment. Implementing robust anti-corruption measures, ensuring the fair and impartial administration of justice, and promoting ethical behavior in public office are essential steps. Furthermore, engaging citizens in governance through participatory processes and ensuring that their voices are heard and valued can significantly enhance trust. The effects of rebuilding government trust are profound. A trustworthy government can foster greater public cooperation, enhance the effectiveness of policies, and create a more stable and cohesive society. It can also boost economic development by creating a predictable and stable environment that attracts investment (Human Rights Watch 2019).

The effectiveness of democratic governance and the level of trust in government institutions are critical determinants of a nation's political stability and socioeconomic development. In Nigeria, a country marked by its rich cultural diversity and significant economic potential, the erosion of public trust in government has been a persistent challenge. Decades of political instability, corruption, and inefficiency have weakened the relationship between the state and its citizens, undermining the very foundation of democracy (Salako and Ajibade 2019). Rebuilding government trust and fostering effective democratic governance is essential for Nigeria's progress. Trust in government is not merely an abstract ideal; it is the bedrock upon which effective policies, civic engagement, and national unity are built. When citizens trust their leaders and institutions, they are more likely to comply with laws, participate in democratic processes, and support public policies. Conversely, widespread distrust can lead to apathy, civil unrest, and the weakening of democratic institutions (World Bank. 2020).

Effective democratic governance, characterized by transparency, accountability, and inclusiveness, can restore faith in governmental institutions. In Nigeria, this involves addressing corruption, ensuring fair and free elections, and improving public service delivery. Strengthening the rule of law and enhancing the capacity of governmental institutions are also crucial steps towards rebuilding trust. Ultimately, rebuilding trust in government is not just about restoring faith in public institutions; it is about laying the foundation for a more inclusive, effective, and resilient democracy (World Bank. 2020).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Nigeria, Africa's most populous country and largest economy continues to face significant challenges in establishing effective democratic governance and rebuilding public trust in government institutions. Despite being a democracy since 1999, Nigeria's political landscape is characterized by persistent issues such as corruption, electoral malpractices, political violence, and weak institutional frameworks. These issues undermine the efficacy of democratic governance and erode public trust in government. Nigeria has consistently ranked low on the Transparency International Corruption Perceptions Index, indicating widespread corruption across various levels of government. This pervasive corruption erodes public confidence in government institutions and processes. Electoral malpractices, including vote buying, ballot stuffing, and intimidation of voters and opposition candidates, are common. These practices compromise the integrity of elections, leading to questions about the legitimacy of elected officials. Political violence and insecurity, often orchestrated by rival political factions, have marred the democratic process.

This violence not only threatens the safety of citizens but also discourages political participation and undermines the democratic process. Government institutions often lack the capacity, independence, and resources needed to function effectively. This results in poor service delivery, inadequate policy implementation, and a lack of accountability. There is a significant trust deficit between the Nigerian populace and their government. Many citizens perceive government officials as self-serving and disconnected from the needs and aspirations of the people. High levels of poverty and unemployment, coupled with regional disparities, exacerbate the sense of disenfranchisement among large segments of the population. This socio-economic inequality fuels discontent and can lead to social unrest.

The cumulative effect of these issues is a weakening of Nigeria's democratic fabric and a hindered socio-economic development. Without effective democratic governance and restoring public trust, efforts to achieve sustainable development, social cohesion, and political stability are significantly compromised. The lack of trust in government can lead to increased apathy, reduced civic participation, and potential for civil unrest, further destabilizing the nation.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Rebuilding Government Trust on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- Examine the effect of fair and free elections on effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria.
- Evaluate the effect of Accountability mechanisms on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria.

1.4 Hypotheses of the Study

- ❖ Fair and free elections have no significant effect on effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria.
- ❖ Accountability mechanisms have no significant effect on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Rebuilding Government Trust

Trust is the bedrock of any functioning democracy, and the role of governance in establishing and maintaining this trust is paramount. In recent years, democracies around the world have faced challenges that have eroded public trust in political institutions. The most generally accepted definition of trust describes it as the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party, based on the expectation that the other party will perform a particular action, irrespective of the trustor's ability to monitor or control. In today's world of governance, society's stability and advancement depend on public confidence in government agencies Diamond, (2008). However, several issues, such as corruption, inefficiency, a lack of transparency, and socioeconomic inequality, have contributed to the erosion of this confidence on a global scale. To provide efficient governance, advance democratic ideals, and maintain a positive connection between the state and its citizens, this trust must be restored. The all-encompassing tactics required to rebuild public confidence in government, with a focus on inclusivity, judicial independence, civic education, media freedom, transparency, involvement, and integrity as well as service delivery. Transparency is one of the main tenets of public trust in governance. Transparency in government allows

citizens to examine the way their government is run, which lowers corruption and increases public trust. Initiatives to make government data easily accessible are essential for enabling citizens to remain informed about the actions and expenditures of their government, Grimmelikhuijsen & Meijer, (2014). Rebuilding trust requires strong citizen participation and effective communication. To involve the public in decision-making processes, governments should host town hall meetings, internet forums, and public consultations, (Johnston, 2014). The public's demands and preferences are reflected in policies thanks to this participatory method. Regaining confidence in the administration is a difficult but attainable objective. It necessitates a multipronged strategy that takes into account issues of judicial independence, media freedom, inclusivity, engagement, openness, integrity, and service delivery, (World Bank, 2020).

Fair and Free Elections

The foundation of democratic government is the holding of fair and free elections. They are essential channels by which people can use their right to vote for representatives and shape the policies of their government. Governments are kept transparent, answerable to the people, and accountable through a strong electoral process. Nonetheless, several essential elements, such as independent institutions, open processes, and engaged citizens, are necessary for the integrity of elections. Fair and free elections depend on a strong institutional and legal foundation. Citizens' rights to vote and run for office must be protected by constitutions and election laws. Independent electoral commissions tasked with regulating the electoral process ought to be established within these frameworks. To maintain objectivity and prevent conflicts of interest, independence is essential. It is imperative to establish efficient legislative frameworks to handle election conflicts and complaints in a timely and transparent manner, (Carter Center, 2020; United Nations, 2016).

Fair and free elections must be inclusive, giving every eligible citizen an equal chance to take part. Ensuring accessibility of voter registration procedures, the absence of discriminatory voting barriers, and the electorate's knowledge of their rights and the election process are all part of this. Disenfranchised groups, like women, individuals with disabilities, and members of ethnic minorities, should be given special consideration. Broad representation and preventing disenfranchisement are two requirements of electoral systems. An essential component of electoral integrity is transparency, (OSCE, 2010). Election procedures must be transparent enough for both local and foreign observers to check that they adhere to accepted norms of justice. To foster public trust, transparency in campaign finance, vote tallying, and results announcement is vital. Accountability procedures must be in place to prevent and deal with electoral malpractice, corruption, and fraud. This entails strong oversight by impartial organizations and severe consequences for infractions, (Carter Center, 2020).

A major threat to election fairness is political violence and intimidation. Against voters, candidates, and election officials, this includes using physical force, threats, and coercion. Preparing a safe and secure electoral environment is critical. To stop and deal with electoral violence in any form, law enforcement, the court system, and civil society must collaborate.

Free and fair elections are essential to democratic societies' ability to function. They give people the power to voice their opinions, demand transparency from their leaders, and shape the course of their government. A

multidimensional strategy that includes inclusivity, transparency, strong legal frameworks, and active civic engagement is needed to ensure voting integrity. Preserving the credibility of elections requires tackling issues like media manipulation, electoral fraud, and political violence. Maintaining free and fair elections is essential to bolstering democracy globally, and this requires both national and international support, (Human Rights Watch, 2019; International Crisis Group, 2018).

Accountability mechanisms

In its simplest form, the word accountability implies being held into account for one's actions. Preston (1992) says it means holding public officials responsible for their actions. Accountability, according to Lawton and Rose (1994), is a process where a person or group of people are required to present an account of their activities and the way in which they have or have not discharged their duties. By inference, a person is held accountable for not only his/her actions but also inactions. To Rouse (1997), accountability entails the demonstration to someone else of success or achievement- it involves revealing, explaining and justifying what one does, or has done, or how one discharges ones responsibilities. In the words of Laxmikanth (2006). "The concept of accountability connotes the obligation of the administrators to give a satisfactory account of their performance and the manner in which they have exercised powers conferred on them". In specific terms, public accountability means the firm recognition and acceptance of the fact that all public officials owe and hold their positions on trust for the people. It implies that those who render public service must account to the people they are expected to serve (Akpan, 1982). Nkoma (2004) maintained that public accountability is the requirement that those who hold public trust should account for the use of that trust to citizens or their representatives

Maintaining the legitimacy and integrity of the electoral process depends on accountability systems. These procedures guarantee that all facets of elections are carried out impartially, openly, and in compliance with the law and other requirements. These procedures aid in the prevention and resolution of electoral fraud, corruption, and other malpractices by holding all stakeholders accountable, including voters, political parties, and candidates. Any effective accountability process must start with a strong legislative framework. Election procedures and dispute resolution processes must be spelled out in constitutions, electoral laws, and regulations, as well as the rights and obligations of every voter. According to the Carter Center (2020), these laws should define the procedures for voter registration, voting, and counting as well as the consequences of breaking electoral regulations. They should also establish impartial electoral commissions.

Accountability is ensured in large part by independent electoral commissioners. These organizations must conduct fair and transparent elections. Electoral commissions must be staffed by people with integrity and experience, be financially independent, and remain immune to political interference to preserve their independence. To avoid conflicts of interest and foster public trust in the election process, these commissions' independence is crucial (International IDEA, 2017). A crucial accountability mechanism is election observation by both domestic and foreign observers, who keep an eye on the electoral process to make sure it follows national and international standards, deter electoral fraud and malpractice, and provide insightful assessments and recommendations for better elections in the future (National Democratic Institute, 2018). For instance, the European Union and the

Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe (OSCE) frequently send out observation missions to keep an eye on elections and evaluate their transparency and fairness (OSCE, 2010).

Another crucial accountability tool is the regulation of political contributions. Rich donors' disproportionate influence is lessened when there are restrictions on the amount of money that people and organizations can contribute to political campaigns. Reducing the need for private donations and promoting justice can both be accomplished by public sponsorship of campaigns (International IDEA, 2019). Ensuring that elections remain credible requires the implementation of efficient dispute-resolution procedures. Complaints and appeals should be handled by electoral commissioners and courts according to defined protocols. These protocols must be accessible to all parties involved, transparent, and timely. According to the United Nations (2016), these measures serve to preserve the electoral process's integrity and guarantee that the results of the election are acknowledged by all sides by rapidly and fairly addressing disputes.

Mechanisms for accountability are essential to maintaining the validity and integrity of elections. To preserve the ideals of free and fair elections, a complete strategy involving strong legislative frameworks, impartial electoral commissions, observation and monitoring, openness in campaign funding, tools to combat electoral fraud, and technological advancements can be implemented. These procedures support the general stability and well-being of democratic regimes by requiring accountability from all parties involved.

Effective Democratic Governance

Democratic governance is a kind of government that places a strong emphasis on citizen participation in decision-making, individual rights protection, and the responsibility of those in positions of authority. Any society that aspires to stability, prosperity, and equity must have effective democratic governance. It encompasses not just how democratic institutions operate but also how values like responsibility, openness, involvement, and the rule of law are upheld. The foundation of democratic governance is accountability. It guarantees that elected officials and other stakeholders will be held accountable for their decisions and actions. Regular elections, judicial supervision, and checks and balances between the branches of government are examples of accountability mechanisms. Holding politicians responsible also requires the existence of robust institutions, such as independent auditors and anti-corruption agencies (International IDEA, 2017).

When governance is transparent, information on choices, actions, and procedures made by the government is available to the public. This transparency makes it possible for the public to have confidence in the administration and to participate in democratic processes with knowledge. Laws requiring the release of public information, the use of digital platforms to make government data accessible, and active media participation can all improve transparency (Transparency International, 2019).

The involvement of citizens is essential to democracy. It entails people actively participating in decision-making procedures, whether by voting, holding open forums, or engaging in civic activity. Encouraging involvement ensures that the population's varied demands and interests are taken into account when making decisions. Meaningful citizen involvement can be facilitated by mechanisms including inclusive policy-making procedures, participatory budgeting, and public forums (CIVICUS, 2017). Ensuring that every person and organization,

including the government, is bound by the law depends on the rule of law. It offers a framework for preventing power abuses, upholding human rights, and justly administering justice. Important elements of the rule of law include respect for the legal system, an impartial court, and efficient law enforcement (United Nations, 2016).

For society to be peaceful, stable, and prosperous, there must be effective democratic governance. Democratic regimes can guarantee that governmental establishments are answerable to the public by preserving the values of popular sovereignty, the rule of law, political pluralism, and human rights. But there are a lot of issues that democratic administration has to deal with, like social inequality, political polarization, and corruption, which call for coordinated action. Societies can ensure that their democratic institutions are robust and continue to serve the interests of all citizens by enacting anti-corruption measures, encouraging civic education and engagement, fostering inclusive political dialogue, and investing in social and economic development.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

Liberal Democratic Theory

The study adopts the Liberal Democratic Theory giving the fact that the organic linkage between democracy and constitutionalism is indispensable in the paradigm of politics and democratic practice. In other words, the modern concept of the constitution is found within the democratic political system of Western liberalism. The doctrine or concepts of liberalism, libertarianism, and or civil liberties are the cardinal principles upon which the Liberal Democratic Theory is built. Each of the concepts attempts to explain a situation of individual freedom within the context of a democratic setting and with constitutional paraphernalia as checks on despotic leadership. This forms the bedrock of democratic governance within which constitutionalism is grafted (Musa, 2013). However, and according to Fairchild (1970, p.76) “Liberal democracy is a combination of various concepts each explaining an aspect of the freedom of the individual within the constitutional provision in the society. Freedom of the individual about those in leadership; and above all freedom of the individual against the undemocratic ruler”.

In another vein, liberalism is regarded as a doctrine of intellectual tolerance that rules out selfish considerations and other evidence of unfairness and bills in the formulation of economic, political, and social policies thus giving special regard to the constitution and constitutionalism in society (Nnoli, 2003). The organization of Western democracy is certainly based on the formulation, respect, and implementation of the provisions of the Constitution. It is undoubtful, therefore, this is why in any political system where the constitution is abused, there can hardly exist democracy of the Western ideals. Civil liberties can be seen as a phrase associated chiefly with the practice of democracy stemming from English institutions in which civil power is dominant over military power and in which judicial review of all confinements is guaranteed by ‘habeas corpus’ (i.e. ‘the rights of man’, ‘civil rights’,) as in English and American law.

The philosophical rationale for the liberal democratic theory of representation, the perceived basis of modern constitutional democracy as one sees it today, can be from the viewpoint that man, as a creature of reason, can identify his interests and his own opinions and is also aware of the wider claims of the community and which can be threatening to democratic governance and national development. By and large, and from the above, man will, therefore, intelligently use his vote and is consequently entitled to share in the selection of representatives (Hoult,

1969). The first requirement of democratic governance is constitutionalism which is found within a legal state framework in which the constitution is a supreme law, a requirement abused in the Nigerian political system.

2.3 Empirical Review

Muhammad M; S. (2012). Conducted a study on Public Trust and Democracy in Nigeria: The Missing Link and its Imperative for Leadership Values. To find out Nigeria's situation, this paper brought to focus a survey study done on Nigeria by Afrobarometer (a collaborative group of social scientists from 18 African countries). The survey which studied the state of public trust in democracy and the nation's leaders showed that many Nigerians have no trust in the nation's political leaders across all levels of government because of their poor performance. But the people still have trust in democracy as the best form of governance for the country. The paper then went ahead to show that the lack of trust brought about a missing link between the people and their leaders; a kind of disconnection between the people and democratic governance. To remedy the situation and possibly restore public trust, the paper called for a renewed democratic leadership that is value-based, virtuous, and focused on public/national interest as against the leaders, usual selfish interest.

Salako and Ajibade (2019). Conducted a study on Analyzing Accountability and Transparency as Major tools for Local Government Administration in Nigeria: A Study of Yewa South Local Government. The study also investigated the effect of these tools which can help promote citizen engagement and participation thereby improving the quality of services delivered. With reliance on primary and secondary data, the paper observed that the goal of improving accountability, transparency, and reducing inefficiency at the local government level should not be viewed in isolation, but as part of the broader issue of governance and public management. The theory of accountability and social contingency theory of accountability proved useful in highlighting issues that affect accountability and transparency in Nigeria's local government administration.

3. Methodology

The study adopts a descriptive research survey. A structured questionnaire design with a five-point Likert scale was used to collect data for the study. The population of this study was the staff of some selected public sectors in Nigeria. Sampling used a purposive sampling technique. The sample size was collected for 217 with consideration of the statistical adequacy of the sample to get 0.8 power with 0.05 alpha. Out of 217 respondents (comprising the staff of the selected public sector to whom the research questionnaire was distributed, only 168 pieces of the questionnaire were returned to the researchers. This means that the respondents' response rate is 77.4%. The remaining 22.6% was not feasible to use because there were some question items that were left empty or were not answered by the respondents (missing value). So, the number of questionnaires analyzed in this study was 168 pieces.

Table 1 shows a summary of the demographic characteristics of the respondents to provide information about the age of respondents, gender of the respondent, educational qualification, professional role, and years of working experience as considered for this study. Additionally, in this study, we tested the conceptual underpinnings of the hypothesis using Smart PLS version 4.0. The analysis was presented transparently and systematically, allowing for comprehension of the conceptual framework and results.

Table 1: Sample Characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	112	66.7%
	Female	56	33.3%
Age(yrs.)	<25yrs	27	16.1%
	25-34yrs	61	36.3%
	35-44yrs	51	30.4%
	>45yrs	29	17.3%
Educational Qualification			
	NCE/OND	47	27.9%
	B.Sc	84	50%
	MSc/MBA	37	22.1%
Professional Role			
		33	19.6%
		93	55.4%
		42	25%
Experience (yrs)			
	1-09yrs	71	42.3%
	10-19yrs	45	26.8%
	20-29yrs	32	19%
	30yrs>	20	11.9%

Measurement

Measurements in the study used a 4-point Likert scale starting from High (4) to Moderate to No (1). The 4-point Likert scale was used because it was easy to respond and required less time consideration to complete when compared to open-ended questions. To measure the variables of institutional factors the following proxies were used organizational structure, internal structure, staff competence, and institutional culture, while political leadership, political stability, and political environment are proxies used to measure political factors.

4. Result and Discussion

The research used PLS-SEM based on primary data collected to find out a direct relationship between the institutional and political factors on the design and implementation of public sector financial management reforms. SmartPLS 4.0 was used to analyze structural equation models. Measurement of the model through an algorithm to explain the variance of the dependent construct. In the first step, the construction score was estimated. Then the final estimation from external loading was also calculated as the structural model of the path coefficient, which results in the R-squared value of the endogenous latent variable.

Table 2: Validity and Reliability Test

Latent Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Fair and Free election in Nigeria.	0.733	0.701	0.831	0.622
Accountability mechanism	0.787	0.787	0.859	0.604
Democratic Governance	0.734	0.739	0.827	0.618

Three primary findings are provided by Smart PLS: latent variable R-squared values, path coefficients for the structural model, and outer loadings for the measurement model. Additionally, the reliability of individual indicators, the average extracted variance, and the composite reliability of internal consistency testing are all considered in the assessment of the measurement.

To determine whether a construct is valid and reliable, hypothesis testing examines the structural relationships between the constructs. Since the Cronbach alpha, or composite reliability, value is larger than 0.7, the result is considered high quality and reliable. When the reliability test yields a result larger than 0.7, it indicates that the value is high and satisfactory. To establish convergent validity, look at the AVE. In Table 2 it can be seen that the AVE value is greater than 0.5, which means that the results are acceptable.

To evaluate the discriminant validity of the 3 variables used in the study, Heterotrait-and Monotrait (HTMT) in Table 3 analysis was executed, while the Fornell-Larcker criterion was examined in Table 4.

Model Assessment

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT)

S/N		Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio
1	Fair and free election <-> Democratic governance in Nigeria	0.567
2	Accountability mechanism<-> Democratic governance in Nigeria	0.419

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	Design and implementation of public sector fin. Mgt reform.	Institutional Factor	Political Factor
Design and implementation of public sector fin. Mgt reform.	0.756		
Institutional Factor	0.623	0.771	
Political Factor	0.234	0.355	0.419

The confirmatory factor analysis's findings, which are presented in table 3, support the empirical evidence for the majority of the variables' uniqueness. It is important to note that the aforementioned table does not show discriminant validity issues by the HTMT_{0.85} criterion. This suggests that collinearity issues between latent constructs were not detected by the HTMT criteria.

Table 5: Factor loadings of the measurement items

	Fair and Free Election	Accountability Mechanism	Democratic governance in Nigeria
FFE1	0.648		
FFE2	0.867		
FFE3	0.827		
AM1		0.771	
AM2		0.787	
AM3		0.809	
AM4		0.740	
DGN1			0.754
DGN2			0.838
DGN3			0.773

Structural Equation Modelling

In Smart-PLS, the measurement model and structural model are often the first two stages used in order to observe the impact of predictor variables on the outcome variable. A few of the criteria, such as construct validity and dependability, have already been covered. In addition to that in the structural modelling equation R square also shown for the predictive ability of predictors variables on the outcome variables. The value of R-squared for the model is 0.497 indicating that 49.7% variation in the democratic governance in Nigeria is caused by fair and free election and accountability mechanisms.

The model fit was tested for the model using the SRMR value which is 0.028 respectively. This means that the model is a good fit.

Table 6: The Direct Effect of Rebuilding Government Trust on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria.

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T-statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Fair and free election <-> Democratic governance in Nigeria	0.686	0.683	0.084	8.193	0.000
Accountability mechanism<- Democratic governance in Nigeria	-0.009	0.020	0.081	0.106	0.916

Summary of findings

The study aimed to identify the effect of effect of Rebuilding Government Trust on Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria. The result of HTMT in Table 3 indicates that the variables are correlated however there

was no presence of multicollinearity within the variables. Table 6 indicates that at a 5% level of significance, there is a statistically significant positive effect of fair and free elections on democratic governance in Nigeria. Also, the result indicates that the accountability mechanism has no statistically significant effect on the democratic governance of Nigeria.

Hypothesis

1. Fair and free elections have no significant effect on the democratic governance of Nigeria

[$\beta=0.686$; T-Statistic = 8.193; P values < 0.001]

[R-Squared = 0.497 (49.7%); SMRM = 0.0028 <0.1]

2. Accountability mechanisms have no significant effect on the design and implementation of public health financial management reforms.

[$\beta=-0.009$; T-Statistic = 0.106; P values =0.916]

[R-Squared = 0.497 (49.7%); SMRM = 0.0028 <0.1]

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the research on Rebuilding Government Trust and Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria reveals significant insights into the dynamics of democratic processes in the country. The findings indicate a statistically significant positive effect of fair and free elections on democratic governance in Nigeria. This underscores the critical importance of electoral integrity in fostering a robust democratic system. Free and fair elections enhance the legitimacy of the government, strengthen public trust, and ensure that the leadership reflects the will of the people, which are essential components of effective democratic governance.

Conversely, the study also shows that the accountability mechanism does not have a statistically significant effect on democratic governance in Nigeria. This suggests that while mechanisms for holding public officials accountable are important, their current implementation in Nigeria may not be sufficient to impact democratic governance significantly. It may indicate issues such as weak institutional frameworks, ineffective enforcement of accountability measures, or public perception problems regarding the efficacy of these mechanisms.

Overall, these findings highlight the crucial role of electoral processes in strengthening democracy in Nigeria, while also pointing to the need for further reforms and enhancements in accountability mechanisms to ensure they effectively contribute to democratic governance. Addressing these gaps can potentially lead to a more transparent, accountable, and democratically governed Nigeria. The study concludes that Rebuilding Government Trust has a significant effect on Democratic Governance in Nigeria.

Recommendation

Based on the findings regarding Rebuilding Government Trust and Effective Democratic Governance in Nigeria, several key recommendations can be made to further enhance democratic governance in the country:

➤ Reforming and enforcing electoral laws to prevent fraud, vote-buying, and other irregularities, and Ensuring the independence and capacity of electoral commissions to conduct elections impartially and effectively. Also Enhancing voter education campaigns to ensure citizens are well-informed about their rights and the importance of participating in elections.

➤ Building the capacity of anti-corruption agencies, judiciary, and oversight bodies to function independently and effectively, and Encouraging greater citizen participation in governance processes, including public hearings, town hall meetings, and community monitoring of government projects. Also Implementing and enforcing laws on public access to information, and ensuring transparency in government procurement and budgeting processes.

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